

Social Variables and Hygiene Practices of Senior Secondary School Students in Calabar Education Zone, Cross River State, Nigeria

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Abstract

The study examined the influence of social variables on hygiene practices among senior secondary school students in Calabar Educational Zone of Cross River State, Nigeria. The study adopted the inferential survey research design. The study was guided by two null hypotheses. The population consisted of all the 20,470 senior secondary school students of 81 public secondary schools during the 2016/2017 academic session. The study adopted a stratified random sampling technique in selecting a sample of 819 students. Social Variables on Hygiene Practices Questionnaire (SVHPQ) was the instrument used for data collection. Mean and standard were used for data analysis. The data collected were analysed using ANOVA and Pearson Product Moment Correlation analysis tested at .05 levels of significance. The study revealed that there is a significant influence of awareness and cultural beliefs on secondary school students' hygiene practices in the Calabar Education Zone of Cross River State. The study concluded that hygiene practices are more of behavioural development rather than economic power and that the awareness of health, social and psychological aspects of good hygiene behaviour are very important. Based on these findings, the study recommended that religious leaders in churches or mosques should be encouraged to engage in constant awareness on proper hygiene practices and buckets of water, soap and towels should be made available in schools to increase the level of cleanliness in students.

Keywords: Awareness, cultural beliefs, hygiene practices, social variables, students' hygiene.

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Introduction

Hygiene refers to a condition or practice by which, people maintain or promote good health by keeping themselves and their surroundings clean. It plays a dominant role in keeping one's personality high. Good hygiene practices influence one's body image, self-esteem, confidence, self-concept and motivation. People with low self-esteem and especially those with depression often neglect personal hygiene practices, which increase the problem of poor body image (Tabbner, 2016). Hygiene practices are healthy behaviour that people undertake to keep themselves and others healthy, as well as to prevent them from disease. It is a public health tool that is used for disease prevention and health promotion in individual, family, communities,

and society at large. Good hygiene practices remain the primary disease prevention strategy through the combined benefit of improved food, quality water, personal cleanness and the hygienic quality of the environment. This can drastically reduce routine exposures to pathogenic and microorganisms. Irrespective of the overwhelming benefits of good hygiene practices students have not yet seen the need to embrace proper personal hygiene as a tool for disease prevention (Aiello, Larson & Sedlack, 2015).

There had been practices of poor hygiene among students in schools and even at home. This often manifests in students neglecting to brush their teeth before going to school, clean their anus after excretion, cut their hairs or wash their hairs. In most cases, uniforms are not washed, food is picked from the ground, fruits are eaten unwashed, hands are not properly washed before and after eating or after making use of the toilet. Fingernails are used to remove food particles from the mouth, as well as playing with insects like flies and contaminated dead animals, non-provision of water in the school toilet in sufficient quantity for the students to wash hands after defecating and flush or clean the toilet, children for weeks will not brush their teeth even when they want to, they use salt and charcoal in place of toothpaste, which is detrimental to their health. This has caused thousands of children their lives, missed schools, repeat classes as well as perform very poor academically due to sickness resulting from poor hygiene practices as well as income burden on treatment.

Governments, as well as non-governmental organizations, have made several efforts in public health education campaigns on personal hygiene practices such as handwashing, safe disposal of wastes, regular bathing, washing and drying of clothes after use, environmental sanitation among others. Despite all these campaigns, the level of hygiene practices especially among school-age children and adolescents in Calabar Education Zone remains very poor. What has continually disturbed the mind of the researcher, some parents and other stakeholders is what probably could have been the cause of this problem? Factors such as knowledge of the relevance of hygienic practices, parental upbringing, peer influence, environmental awareness among others have been identified to be responsible for this low level of hygiene practices. To this end, the researcher sought to ascertain whether cultural beliefs and level of awareness might be responsible for the poor hygiene practices among senior secondary school students in Calabar Education Zone.

Culture is an inherited element that man comes to meet, but can be changed, adjusted or forgotten. It is most times make-up or builds an individual, which are avenues for character formation and acceptance level (Hodes, 2016). Culture is a shared and organised body of customs, skills, ideas and values transmitted socially from one generation to another (Dunning, 2006). Cultural norms may interfere with proper hygiene practices by altering individual perceptions of diseases and treatments (Slade, 2014). For instance, the spread of opisthorchiasis viverrini, a common foodborne parasite in South East Asia was directly linked to the cultural habit of eating raw and fermented fish dishes and this greatly affects one's health (Slade, 2014).

Grayon, Durce and Johnson (2009) stated that personal hygiene practices including covering the mouth when sneezing or coughing, appropriate disposal of tissues, hand cleaning

with soap/alcohol biocides (hand-washing) and other hygiene practices such as washing utensils are widely recommended for reducing infectious disease. Grayson et al. posited that the benefit of adhering to hygiene practices are greatly hindered by the level of awareness. A proper level of awareness and effective hygiene practices reduce the risk of becoming exposed to infectious disease capable of reducing the quality of life and can even lead to more deaths than famine, accident and crime put together. Sidibe and Curtis (2017) posited that awareness of health, social and psychological aspects of good hygiene behaviour are very important. World Bank (2016) reported that contaminated household environment and risky hygiene practices account for about 30% of the burden of infectious disease in developing countries. The organization explained that within this group 75% of all lives lost yearly are due to poor sanitation and the prevalence of risky hygiene behaviour.

The mere provision of water supply and sanitation facilities is not enough to bring down the morbidity rate, but the level of awareness and attitude towards utilization of water and sanitation facilities linked with proper hygiene knowledge and practice has proven to be more effective in reducing transmission of disease (Bloomfield, 2017). William (2017) stated that good oral hygiene prevents sores and bad breath and keep mucous membranes from becoming dry and cracked. The scholar added that poor knowledge of oral hygiene practices can contribute to poor appetite, as the bacteria in the mouth can cause pneumonia, inflamed gums which initiate an inflammatory process that puts a strain on the heart and decreases resistance to infection. As maintained by Slade (2013) good knowledge as well as proper oral hygiene practices (proper tooth brushing techniques, thorough washing of mouth with water after brushing) prevent conditions such as gingivitis, tooth decay and tooth abrasion which may directly affect organs in the body. Aiello, et al. (2015) argued that proper hygiene practices are anchored on the availability of resources and materials used in hygiene practices not the level of awareness.

Idowu (2013) showed that 52.3% of nursing mothers did not know about washing their hands after changing baby's napkin, as well as having a low knowledge of handwashing hygiene practices before and after preparing food. The researcher also noted that 26.1% had the knowledge of washing their hands but they wash their hands without using soap while 21.6% used the same water they use to bathe their baby to wash their hands and their wrapper is used ash and drying material. Hodes (2016) revealed that students with high parity of hygiene knowledge practice good hand hygiene more than their counterpart of lower parity. A report from the World Health Organization (2014) revealed that 87.8% of the total population studied had little or knowledge of handwashing with soap after playing, visiting or making use of the toilet, cutting and washing of fingernails.

It is of this background that this study is set to examine the influence of cultural belief and the level of awareness of hygiene practices among senior secondary school students in Calabar Educational Zone of Cross River State, Nigeria. Students, the general public, school management, curriculum developers and society as a whole can profit greatly from the results of this study. The results can allow students to identify the difficulties of inadequate hygienic practices, helping them to find out how well compliance with correct hygiene practices might

be optimal for health, via the prevention of infectious diseases. The study will offer the general public with information on appropriate sanitary measures and on domestic hygiene practices. The government will provide a free environment for infection for students and will establish a pathway for public health campaigns for the cleanliness of students through the study's results and recommendations. Through the results the curriculum planner will ensure that hygiene practice is included in school curricula for the children to be taught. This would build the information, skills and attitudes essential for kids to practice cleanliness.

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were tested statistically.

- i. The level of awareness has no significant influence on hygiene practices among secondary school students in the Calabar Education Zone of Cross River State.
- ii. Cultural believes do not have any significant influence on hygiene practices among secondary school students in Calabar Education Zone of Cross River State.

Methods

This study was based on an inferential survey research approach. Due to the sample from the population acquired and to the results adapted for the total population, the design was thought suitable for the survey. The study data has been obtained using a standardized questionnaire particularly tailored for this study. There are 81 public secondary schools in the 7 Local Government Areas in Calabar Education Zone, in the state of the Calabar River, consisting of all high school pupils (SS I, SS II and SS III). In the academic semester for 2016/2017 there were roughly 20,470 (9,331 males and 11,139 females).

A stratified random sample strategy was used in this investigation. This was the first way to arrange schools in the area in seven classrooms based on the local government region. By use of the hat and drawing technique (balloting) 20 percent of schools were picked at random by the researcher in each of the LGAs and the schools were the schools selected. In this regard, four of Akamkpa LGA's schools were selected: one from Akpabuyo, Bakassi, Calabar South LGAs, and three from Biase, Calabar and Odukpani LGA. In all, seventeen schools of the seven LGAs of the Calabar Education Zone were selected and these were the sampled schools. The study's sample includes 819 students (387 males and 432 females), or roughly 4% of all senior high school students in the Calabar Educational Zone of Cross River State.

The data was collected using a researcher-created questionnaire called the Social Variables and Hygiene Practices Questionnaire (SVHPQ). On a four-point Likert scale of strongly agree, agree, disagree, and strongly disagree, the instrument consists of 28 items meant to examine social characteristics and hygiene behaviours (SA, A, D, SD). The items were arranged according to the study's independent variables. Two experts from the University of Calabar's Measurement and Evaluation Department assessed the instrument for face and

content validity. The reliability estimate coefficient varied from .72 to .80 when using the Cronbach alpha estimate technique.

The instrument was given to the students who were randomly selected. The researcher described the purpose of the questionnaire in full and gave the students the option of participating or not participating in the study. They were given time, and 763 out of the original 819 copies of the questionnaires distributed to the pupils were successfully collected. This resulted in a return rate of 93.16 percent. The data was analysed using one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) and Pearson Product Moment Correlation analysis, both of which were assessed for significance at the .05 level.

Results

Hypothesis 1

The level of awareness has no significant influence on hygiene practices among secondary school students in the Calabar Education Zone of Cross River State. Based on this, the influence of level of awareness on hygiene practices was computed using One-way ANOVA as shown in Table 1.

Table 1. One-way Analysis of Variance of the level of awareness and hygiene practices among secondary school students in Calabar Education Zone of Cross River State

Level of awareness	N	Mean	SD		
Low	204	29.51	7.11		
Moderate	388	32.21	4.5		
High	171	34.32	3.44		
Total	763	31.96	5.41		
Source of variance	SS	df	Mean square	F-ratio	p-level
Between groups	2192.332	2	1096.166	41.415*	.000
Within groups	20115.41	760	26.468		
Total	22307.74	762			

*Significant at .05 alpha level; $p < .05$.

The result presented in Table 1 revealed the mean score obtained by the subjects who have a low level of awareness as regards to their hygiene practices was 29.51 with a standard deviation of 7.11 which is less than the mean score of 32.21 with a standard deviation of 4.50 obtained by the subjects who have a moderate level of awareness and this is less than the mean score of 34.32 with a standard deviation of 3.44 obtained by the subjects who have a high level of awareness. This implies that the higher the awareness level, the higher the hygiene practices among the students. The result further revealed that the calculated F-value of 41.415 obtained with a p-value of .000 was seen to be greater than F-value tabulated (3.00) with the degrees of freedom of 2 and 760 at a .05 significance level. Therefore, this study rejected the null hypothesis based on the F-values and concluded that the level of awareness of hygiene practices is significant. Given the significant F-value, the Fisher's least significance difference (LSD) was employed as a post hoc test as shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Fisher's Least Significance Difference (LSD) for the level of awareness and hygiene practices among secondary school students in Calabar Education Zone of Cross River State

Level of awareness	N	Mean	MD	p-level
Low	204	29.51	-2.69*	.000
Moderate	388	32.21		
Low	204	29.51	-4.80*	.000
High	171	34.32		
Moderate	388	32.21	-2.11*	.000
High	171	34.32		

*Significant at .05 level; $p < .05$.

The result in Table 2 revealed that there was a significant mean difference in an absolute sense in hygiene practices between subjects whose level of awareness is low and those whose level of awareness is moderate (MD = -2.69, $p < .05$). A Significant mean difference in hygiene practices also exists in absolute sense between subjects whose level of awareness is low and those whose level of awareness is high (MD = -4.80, $p < .05$). Also, a significant mean difference in an absolute sense exists in hygiene practices between subjects whose level of awareness is moderate and those whose level of awareness is high (MD = -2.11, $p < .05$).

Hypotheses 2

Cultural believes do not have any significant influence on hygiene practices among secondary school students in Calabar Education Zone of Cross River State. To test this hypothesis, cultural believes and hygiene practices among Secondary School Students in the Calabar Education Zone of Cross River State were compared using Pearson Product Moment Correlation. The result of the analysis is presented in Table 3.

Table 3. Pearson Product Moment Correlation analysis of cultural believes and hygiene practices among secondary school students in Calabar Education Zone of Cross River State (N=763)

Variables	Mean	SD	r-ratio	p-level
Cultural believes (X)	19.07	2.85		
Hygiene practices (Y)	31.96	5.41	.174*	.000

*Significant at .05. $p < .05$; critical r-value=.088.

The result of the analysis in Table 3 revealed that the cultural believes of the subjects produced a mean score of 19.07 with a standard deviation of 2.85 while their hygiene practices produced a mean score of 31.96 with a standard deviation of 5.41. The result further revealed that the calculated r-ratio of .174 obtained with a p-value of .000 is greater than the critical value of .088 and this met the condition required for significance at the .05 level. Hence, the null hypothesis was rejected. This indicated that a positively significant relationship exists between cultural beliefs and hygiene practices among Secondary School Students in the Calabar Education Zone of Cross River State.

Discussion

Level of awareness and students' hygiene practices

This research hypothesis which addresses the influence of level of awareness on students' hygiene practices revealed that there is a significant influence of awareness on secondary school students' hygiene practices in Calabar Education Zone of Cross River State. This implies that there is a significant influence of level of awareness on hygiene practices among students. This could be since the level of awareness a student has determined his actions. Most students have acquired information on how to maintain the best hygienic condition either through media, interaction and education.

Their practices, therefore, differ compare to students who are restricted in their confines and do not have knowledge of the effect of certain practices like picking food from the ground, not washing your hands after using the toilet among others. This result is in tandem with the finding of Sidibe and Curtis (2017) who noted that awareness of health, social and psychological aspects of good hygiene behaviour are very important. They also noted that the degree of sustainability of the intervention in hygiene practices is the amount of awareness given to students. Stressing that perception strongly influenced one's belief and practices. While explaining that a low level of awareness and behaviour is a major setback in developing countries regarding proper hygiene practices. In addition to having proper resources and facilities, hygiene practices are heavily influenced by students' level of awareness and attitudes towards hygiene.

This result is also in agreement with Bloomfield (2017) that mere provision of water supply and sanitation facilities is not enough to bring down morbidity rate, but the level of awareness and attitude towards utilization of water and sanitation facilities linked with proper hygiene knowledge and practice has proven to be more effective in reducing the transmission of disease. The result also supports Idowu (2013) who noted that hand-washing, as well as cutting and washing of fingernails with soap and water, under personal health, have attracted more attention due to their effectiveness in reducing the spread of disease, stressing that the awareness of handwashing hygiene practices as a medium used in reducing disease transmission is still very poor among nursing mothers. Good oral hygiene prevents sores and bad breath and keeps mucous membranes from becoming dry and cracked. A low level of awareness of oral hygiene practices contributes to poor appetite as the bacteria in the mouth can cause pneumonia, inflamed gums which initiate an inflammatory process that puts a strain on the heart and decreases resistance to infection.

The results also agree with Grayon Melvani, Durce, Barr and Johnson (2009) that personal hygiene practices including covering the mouth when sneezing or coughing, appropriate disposal of tissues, hand cleaning with soap/alcohol biocides (hand-washing) and other hygiene practices such as washing utensils are widely recommended as part of awareness

for reducing infectious disease. Poor knowledge and practice of personal hygiene have a negative consequence for a child's long term overall development.

Cultural beliefs and students' hygiene practices

This research hypothesis which addresses the relationship between cultural believes and hygiene practices revealed that there is a significant positive relationship between cultural beliefs and hygiene practices of students in Calabar Education Zone. This might be a result of the fact that the students hold strong to their cultural beliefs which indicated that the students believe in their culture because it's in support of personal hygiene. This result is not in conformity with the finding of the study by Slade (2014) which stated that cultural norms may interfere with proper hygiene practices by altering individual perceptions of diseases and treatments. For example, the traditional month of postpartum in China is a period where women remain at home and their behaviour to diet, activity and hygiene behaviour is determined by tradition and the theory behind traditional Chinese medicine which underlines some of these beliefs and practice.

Women during this period are not allowed to change their mourning black clothes for months, even when the clothes are dirty. They do not come out and take their bath, they only do that once a day usually at night and this practice has a greater negative influence on hygiene practices. Continuous wearing of dirty clothes is a host for bacteria to build on which eventually transferred to the sensitive part of the skin, causing eczema, acne, among other diseases. This result also agrees with Hodes (2016) who noted that since culture is a way of life of any individual, which most times is connected to the place that person lives and the people around him which in turn can make up or build an individual, which creates ways for character formation and acceptance level.

Conclusion

The study examined the influence of social variables on hygiene practices among senior secondary school students in Calabar Educational Zone of Cross River State, Nigeria. Based on the findings of the study, is concluded that hygiene practices are more of behavioural development rather than economic power. The awareness of health, social and psychological aspects of good hygiene behaviour are very important. Again, there is a significant relationship between cultural beliefs and hygiene practices among secondary school students.

Recommendations

Based on this conclusion, it is recommended that awareness of student's hygiene practices should not only be left for the parents alone. Religious leaders in churches or mosques should be encouraged to engage in constant awareness on proper hygiene practices and buckets of water, soap and towels should be made available in schools to increase the level of cleanliness

in students. The study also recommends that cultural beliefs that impede proper hygiene practices such as regular washing of hands, food warming before eating, among others should be discouraged.

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